

MEDICAL SCIENCES

RISK FACTOR FOR GENERALIZED PERIODONTAL LESIONS IN YOUNG PEOPLE WITH OBESITY

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Abstract

In young obese individuals with generalized periodontitis, abnormalities in protein, fat and carbohydrate metabolism are detected, which contributes to the early destruction of the periodontal tissue complex and rapid tooth loss. Theoretical models of eating disorders are based on the hypothesis that overweight people are unable to regulate their emotions, so turning to food serves as an attempt to avoid or alleviate emotional stress.

Keywords: *generalized periodontitis, obesity.*

Assessing the quality of life of obese patients is necessary to gain a deeper understanding of the stress factors that affect both body and dental health, including periodontal tissue. The purpose of the study is to evaluate quality of life in a situational analysis of risk factors for generalized periodontal disease in young obese individuals with disorders. 19 to 35 years old diagnosed with obesity by age, of which 60 people with generalized periodontitis of the initial I degree and 30 people with generalized chronic catarrhal gingivitis. The control group consisted of 32 practically healthy people with normal weight without eating disorders, with clinically intact periodontium. To identify types of eating disorders, we used the DEBQ (Holland) eating behavior study method and a quality of life survey using the GIQLI questionnaire. An anthropometric study of all patients was carried out, including measurement of height, body weight, and calculation of body mass index (BMI). Results and its discussion. In 75.6% of obese patients (68 people), quality of life indicators according to the GIQLI questionnaire were lower than in the control group (12.5%). The discrepancy between this indicator in persons with generalized periodontitis and generalized chronic gingivitis was not significant. Eating disorders occurred both in obesity (91.1% of cases, 82 people) and in the control group (62.5% of cases, 20 people). According to the Taylor anxiety scale, almost 84 examined obese patients (93.3%) showed an average level of anxiety with a tendency to high: 18.9 ± 1.82 points ($p > 0.05$). 5 patients (5.6%) were found to have a high level of anxiety and one person (1.1%) had a very high level of anxiety. Analysis of the data obtained showed that eating disorders in patients with generalized periodontal lesions and obesity occurred in 90.6% of cases, and in 63.6% a mixed type was found. Most patients have anxiety and depressive

disorders and reduced quality of life. Key words: obesity, risk factors, eating disorders, quality of life, periodontitis, gingivitis

Periodontal diseases among the adult population of Ukraine have a significant prevalence and among people 35-44 years old they occur from 92 to 98% [3]. From the point of view of analyzing the full picture of periodontal diseases and the overall effectiveness of dental care for the population, the standard group for monitoring the dental health of adults usually selects the age group of 35-44 years; the age group of 19-35 years practically falls out of the observation range of most researchers [6]. However, the active formation of inflammatory-dystrophic periodontal lesions occurs precisely at a young age (19-35 years) [3]. Among the causes of pathological changes in periodontal tissues, both local and general factors are distinguished. Common ones include diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, obesity, cardiovascular disorders, metabolic syndrome, and pathology of the endocrine system. Local causes: unsanitized oral cavity, bad habits, dental plaque, traumatic occlusion and imperfect restorations and dentures [4]. -nation of the periodontal tissue complex and rapid loss of teeth [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. At a young age, obese individuals experience a state of chronic stress, which leads to depletion of the body's antioxidant systems and the development of oxidative stress [9]. In turn, this pathological condition maintains a state of chronic inflammation in the macroorganism, which negatively affects the periodontium and the severity of major dental diseases. The pathogenic effects of a damaging factor (stress, depression, etc.) are counteracted by the body's antioxidant system, limiting tissue damage. The role of leading pathogenetic mechanisms in the high sensitivity of the oral cavity to stress factors, in particular the bone tissue of the oral cavity, has been proven, causing

the development of osteoporosis [4]. that cause overeating [1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 9]. This, in turn, is characterized by a violation of the body's homeostasis and the development of psychosomatic diseases. Restrictive eating behavior is characterized by deliberate efforts to achieve or maintain a desired weight through self-restraint. With emotiogenic eating behavior, the desire to eat arises in response to negative emotional states, and with an external desire to eat, it is stimulated not by a real feeling of hunger, but by the appearance of food, its smell, texture, or the sight of other people eating food [12]. oh avoid emotional stress or soften it. Most researchers believe that the inability to adequately cope with emotional states may be the underlying psychological process that defines eating disorders [16]. A kind of emotional intolerance concerns all intense emotional states, including positive (for example, joyful excitement) and negative (for example, depression, anger, anxiety). For people with eating disorders, overeating most often serves as an attempt to regulate these emotions. However, researchers note a high prevalence of alexithymia (limited ability to express emotions) in overweight and obese individuals [14]. It is, as a rule, combined with depression and, when eating, acts in this category of patients as a certain "internal regulator of psychological stress." Wheeler and R. Broad consider alexithymia as a factor that is not only responsible for the tendency to obesity, but also makes it difficult to lose excess weight [14]. Medical psychology and psychiatry have conducted research on various aspects of psychopathology in eating disorders and obesity. [2, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11]. In these studies, personality and psychological characteristics were examined using various clinical tests and instruments: Minnesota Multidimensional Personality Inventory (MMPI), Hessian Personality Inventory (GPI), Spielberger Anxiety Rating Scale, Depression Rating Scale, and TA. However, the results obtained in these studies characterize to a greater extent the level and nature of psychopathological disorders in obese women than personality traits specific to this category of patients. Quality of life is a universal multi-component indicator that reflects the degree of adverse impact of the disease on a person's daily life. The appearance of overweight people becomes a barrier to achieving goals in four important areas - self-perception, intimate-personal, professional and the struggle to maintain health [12, 16]. When assessing the quality of life, it is necessary to determine the general state of health, certain symptoms of the disease, the patient's capabilities (self-care, performance, doing what he loves, etc.); the patient's feelings of general well-being, plans for the future, and the need for medical and social assistance are assessed. Researchers use specially created questionnaires for this purpose (SF-36, GIQLI, etc.). Taking this into account, the purpose of this piece of research was formulated. 60 people with generalized periodontitis of initial stage I and 30 people with generalized chronic catarrhal gingivitis. When diagnosing periodontal lesions, we used the state-dart algorithm of clinical and radiological examination and the classification of M.F. Danilevsky (1994). The control group consisted of 32 practically healthy individuals with nor-

mal weight without eating disorders, with clinically intact periodontium. The survey was conducted with informed consent in accordance with the requirements of the Commission on Bioethical Expertise. All patients were familiarized with the goals and objectives of the study and voluntarily signed informed consent. The criteria for inclusion in the study were: age (19–35 years), patients with obesity (body mass index ≥ 25 kg/m²) and generalized periodontitis of initial - I degree with generalized gingivitis. acute inflammatory diseases and exacerbation of chronic inflammatory diseases at the time of the study, severe somatic diseases that prevent the examination (acute myocardial infarction, acute cerebrovascular accident, malignant neoplasms, etc.), and the formal absence of diagnosed affective disorders. restrictive (first 10 questions), emotiogenic (next 13 questions) and external (other 10 questions) types of eating behavior. The technique consists of 33 questions, each of which has 5 answer options: "never", "rarely", "sometimes", "often", "very often", which are rated on a scale from 1 to 5, with the exception of 31 points that have reverse values. Scores for each scale were calculated by compiling scores for each item and dividing the resulting sum by the number of items in a given scale. The normal values for restrictive, emotiogenic and external types of eating behavior for people with normal body weight are 2.4; 1.8 and 2.7 points respectively. In addition, patients were tested to determine their level of anxiety (Taylor tri-vogue scale) and level of depression (Beck scale). The results of the questionnaire on the Taylor Anxiety Scale were assessed as follows: 40–50 points were considered as an indicator of a very high level of anxiety; 20–40 points indicated a high level of anxiety; 15–25 points – about average (with a tendency to high); 5–15 points indicate an average level of anxiety (with a tendency to low) and 0–5 points indicate a low level of anxiety [13]. The quality of life of patients with morbid obesity was assessed using the Gastrointestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI) questionnaire. The GIQLI questionnaire was created by the authors of EypaschE. et al. and tested in 1993. This questionnaire was developed for gastroenterological patients, but it can also be used for other diseases [17]. The GIQLI questionnaire consists of 36 questions, which are grouped into 5 sections: functional state, emotional state, social activity, influence of treatment and disease - specific questions. The proposed answer options include a 5-rank scale - from 0 to 4, with 0 being the worst value and 4 being the best. The maximum possible number of points is 144. An anthropometric study of all patients was carried out, including measurement of height, body weight, and calculation of body mass index (BMI). Statistical data analysis was carried out using standard software packages (Statistica, MS Excel) for personal computers. Statistical hypothesis testing was performed at a critical level of $p = 0.05$. Results and discussion In 75.6% of obese patients (68 people), quality of life indicators according to the GIQLI questionnaire were lower than in the control group (12.5%, 4 people). The discrepancy between this indicator in persons with generalized periodontitis and generalized chronic gingivitis was not significant.

Analysis of the data obtained showed that eating disorders occurred both in obesity (91.1% of cases, 82 people) and in the control group (62.5% of cases, 20 people). A rational type of eating behavior was rare in both groups of subjects, which indicated the need for further observation and correction, and training in the principles of rational nutrition. (9 people) in the control group. In the control group, the degree of restrictive eating behavior was 2.55 ± 0.09 points. as well as an increased risk of depression. In obesity, the degree of restrictive eating behavior is high: 3.16 ± 0.02 points. Emotional eating behavior was also observed in the control group – in 12.5% (4 people), the degree of manifestation was 1.98 ± 0.06 points. 48.9% (44 people) ($p = 0.05$) with a degree of 3.19 ± 0.02 points (with a norm of 2.7). The high frequency of this disorder indicates the patient's dependence on external factors and circumstances, and not on the internal homeostasis of the body. In the control group, external eating behavior occurred in 37.5% (12 people), the degree of violation was 2.82 ± 0.24 points. Thus, it was found that patients with obesity had eating disorders significantly more often than in the control group. These disorders can be considered as prerequisites contributing to the formation of the underlying disease, obesity, and associated pathological conditions, in particular generalized periodontal lesions, as well as factors aggravating the clinical picture and prognosis of comorbid pathology. The obtained data must be taken into account when carrying out rehabilitation measures in young obese individuals at risk of generalized periodontal diseases. 0.05). 5 patients (5.6%) were found to have a high level of anxiety and one person (1.1%) had a very high level of anxiety. According to the results of the questionnaire on the Beck scale, in general, the average indicators ($M \pm m$) in the obesity group corresponded to subdepression. It turned out that the number of patients without

depression was significantly higher among patients in the control group than among patients in the obese group. Subdepression was detected in 50 patients from the obese group (55.6%), and a moderate level of depression in only 4 (12.5%) patients from the control group. An average level of depression was detected in 2 patients from the control group (6.25%) and in 36 (40.0%) patients with obesity ($p > 0.05$). Thus, the results of the study indicate the importance of psychological factors in the etiology of the formation of overweight and obesity and comorbid pathology. Of particular importance is the role of chronic stress and depression as risk factors for the incidence of generalized periodontal diseases associated with obesity, causing the development of osteoporosis and subsequent tooth loss. Low assessment of quality of life is an additional risk factor and component of pathogenesis. Analysis of the data obtained showed that eating disorders in patients with generalized periodontal diseases associated with obesity occurred in 91.1% of cases, which can be considered as a dictator in the formation of not only obesity, but also the panoply of periodontal pathology.2. Most patients with generalized periodontal diseases associated with obesity have an average level of anxiety and depression.

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